

The Effect of the Lorenz Coefficient on the Free Electron Laser

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Abstract:

Coherent, high-peak tunable power supplies have been very useful in many applications. In this research, the physical process of a new type of coherent, flexible, and very bright radiation source called the free electron laser (sFEL) is described. The movement of the electron beam in the presence of two fields, optical and wave, leads to the exchange of energy. This energy exchange leads to the formation of groups of electrons that will emit very bright radiation. In principle, the resonance wavelength can be adjusted to any radiation area, and this is possible by changing the wave parameter

or the energy of the electron beam. The emitted linear shape has the characteristic shape of short time emission process.

Keywords: *free electron laser, high-peak tunable power, energy exchange.*

Introduction

FEL differs in several ways from other types of lasers. Although, like all types of lasers, it is based on the principle (light amplification by stimulated emission of radiation), the dose of stimulated emission that occurs when transitioning between bound electron states. In fact, the process of emission and stimulated gain depends on in a free electron laser, the electron beam interacts with radiation in a vacuum. Free electron lasers have developed rapidly over the past 30 years. At present there are two main areas for future development of FEL: In the mid-1970s, John Madey and his colleagues built the first free electron laser (FEL) that operated in

the infrared wavelength range. Since that time, tremendous progress has been made in FEL technology. Free electron lasers are sources of synchrotron radiation that can produce radiation with peak power and brightness levels greater than radiation produced by conventional sources such as dipoles and oscillators. Where laser devices are directed the shorter wavelength, higher average power of the short-wavelength free electron is mainly towards the X-ray regime with wavelengths up to 1 enkstrom. Such a source of laser-like coherent.

A Historical Overview of the Free Electron Laser

Spontaneous emission at visible wavelengths and coherent radiation was demonstrated in the early 1950s using radio-frequency and wavelength lines. In 1957, Hansmutz, a researcher at Stanford University, was the first to calculate the acceleration rate of the emission spectrum of electronic radiation. In 1957, Robert Phillips was influential in the development of the maser (microwave amplification by stimulated emission) by applying the principle of an undulating magnetic field. Between 1957 and 1964, a free electron sensor called "Opitron" (for undulating radiation reaction) was demonstrated. In the mid-1970s, John Madey and his colleagues built the first free electron laser and it was given this name because the electrons are not bound to any optical medium such as atoms and crystal molecules. Five years later, Coulson published a description using classical mechanics. It was experimentally verified in 1976. Also in the same year, Coulson solved the electron motion equation using the Lorentz force equation.

In 1978, Wand particle analysis was developed. In fact, Bayer and Milstein analyzed the motion of electrons in a constant periodic magnetic field in the presence of radiation to derive the gain equation. In 1979, Bambini, Rainieri, and Stenholm found it appropriate to treat the problem in a moving frame, where the periodic structure appears as a radiation field with a frequency equal to the frequency of the stimulated beam. In 1980, a physical experiment was conducted to accelerate laser-driven electrons. In 1988 Claudiopil Pellegrini discussed the physics of collective instabilities in particle beams for FELs. In 1989, J.P. Murphy analyzed the effects of coherent synchrotron radiation. In 1990, M. Yasumoto analyzed the evolution of the pulse shape due to the initiation process in a high-gain free electron laser. In 1992, a simple model of the initiation process using a high-gain free electron laser was presented.

In 1993, Fujimoto studied the focusing properties of the far-infrared planar oscillator. In 1996, Alexander Artemiev, Mikhail Fedorov,

and Yuri Rostovtsev's drift region considered the scheme of two non-coupled oscillators with a magnetic medium and a FEL structure without inversion.

In 1998, Hiroshi Takahashi presented a quantum theory of FEL that was first obtained using the double green function method. In 1999 it was decided to build a photoinjector testing facility

In 2000, the first experimental demonstration of second-generation laser, in 2003, ALKhesbakS.H. studied the effect of wave geometric design parameters on the output of a free electron laser.

The Main Rules for Operating a Free Electron Laser Amplifier

The concept of the laser electron free electron laser is a relatively different laser that produces space amplification in the time of a magnetic oscillator. The free electron laser converts the kinetic energy of the relativistic electron beam, which produces a magnetic field Zim Bawazzazza the miracle (accelerators) Storage ring, electromagnetic radiation, Kalmzechrotron, radiofrequency, and RF Lenszak, EM. The transformation occurs when the beam passes through an alternating magnetic field produced by a magnet called the undulator, which forces the electrons to spin. The mixture is mixed and the electrons separate and separate the difference between it and the traditional laser is the use of a relativistic electron beam as a laser medium instead of the effective laser medium.

It consists of:

- A beam of electron accelerator
- corrugated undulator
- magnetic field

Amplification process:

With the electron, but the wave field (magnetic field) does not exchange energy. It controls the determination of its path, as mentioned previously. Energy is exchanged between the electron and the wave with the plane wave, which leads to changes in the plane energy, as the exchange of electron energy not only leads

to the redistribution of the electron's positions. along the axis of the corrugation, where the faster electrons catch up with the slower electrons. A significant exchange of energy can only occur when the strength of the radial oscillator field on the relativistic electrons is nearly resonant. The electrons that gain energy begin to move in front of the average electron while the electrons that lose energy begin to Regress from the mean. When the faster electrons move forward and the slower electrons move backward, the beam is collected periodically on the wavelength scale of the radiation, as the loss and gain of electron energy is repeated throughout the electron beam across many radiation wavelengths. The beam is collected on the radiation wavelength scale. Therefore, the field amplitude the input EM wave grows due to the coherent radiation of equal space electron beams, and the field is amplified. That is, radiation amplification occurs when the radiation emitted by the electrons interact with each other coherently within the

corrugation, which leads to the enhancement of the emitted light beam.

Types of Free Electron Lasers

FEL devices can be divided into two categories (free-electron laser amplifiers and free-electron laser oscillators)

Free Electron Laser Amplifiers (FELAs)

It is a type of free electron laser that works to amplify the radiation through the interaction between the electron beam and the wave. In free electron laser amplifiers, the electron beam passes through a wave, where it emits coherent radiation due to the rotating magnetic field. This emitted radiation can interact with the electron beam, which leads to Amplification through stimulated emission This type of FELAs has various applications including in research, industry and medicine where intense and tunable sources of radiation are needed.

Figure 1. Represents a Free Electron Laser Amplifier

Free Electron Laser Oscillators (FELOs)

It is a subtype of free electron lasers designed to generate coherent and tunable radiation in a continuous and stable wave mode. In free electron laser oscillators, the electron beam passes through a undulator where it interacts with the transverse optical mode of the optical cavity. This interaction results in the emission of

radiation. The radiation is reflected back and forth within the cavity. Confined within a coherent cavity and inflating with each pass until it reaches a stable oscillatory state, FELOs offer advantages such as high energy, wide tunability and narrow linewidths making them suitable for various applications including spectroscopy, materials processing and medical applications

Figure 2. Represents a Free Electron Laser Oscillator

Characteristics of the Free Electron Laser

Each type of laser has its own set of advantages and applications, and the choice between them depends on several factors such as the required wavelength range, power, pulse duration, and operating conditions. Tunable wavelengths: FELs provide tunable wavelengths across a wide range of the electromagnetic spectrum from (microwaves to x-rays) Another characteristic of the free electron laser is its high energy, meaning it can deliver high-energy beams, which makes it useful for various applications such as materials processing, spectroscopy, and medical research.

The free electron laser has unique properties and advantages, each type of laser has its own set of advantages and applications, and the choice between them depends on several factors such as the required wavelength range, power, pulse duration, and operating conditions. The free electron laser can also control the pulse duration, as FELs can produce very short light pulses with a duration of up to 10 minus 15 seconds per second, which allows the study of ultra-fast processes in physics, chemistry and biology. Accordingly, the free electron laser (FEL) is defined as a source of light that relies on high-energy electron beams that produce coherent electromagnetic laser waves with continuous tunability and a short pulse duration. The wavelength of the FEL ranges from millimeters to x-rays, depending on the energy of the electron.

Theory and Results

One-Dimensional Theory of the Free-Electron Laser Amplifier

Field equations and motion equations must be solved simultaneously. from where Principle, Modern supercomputers allow direct simulation of the FEL process. The results of this simulation depend on a large number of problem parameters. It provides the possibility of obtaining a numerical answer for a specific set of data Input, but it hardly helps in understanding the physics of FEL. Can't get A deeper look into the physics of FEL by introducing some simplifying assumptions about the properties of the electron beam and the electromagnetic field. Single model Dimension is an important model from a methodological point of view, there are four assumptions used in the unilateral steady-state model Dimension FEL. amplifier

1. The electron beam has a uniform distribution of intensity in the direction perpendicular to Wave axis
2. Electrons move along identical paths parallel to the wave axis.
3. An amplified wave is a single-color plane wave
4. Infinitely long electron beam This model allows one to study the ideal mechanism of amplification.

Theoretical analyzes of FEL experiments have, so far, been able to treat the collective system only within the limits of an ideal one-dimensional wave field, which is valid only as

long as the radius of the electron beam is much shorter than the period of the wave.

-The small signal gain of a free electron laser is usually calculated using a one-dimensional model, a free electron small signal system. It is analyzed.

Taking diffraction in an electron laser in order to operate at a single frequency and with a uniform wavelength, is taken into account.

Electron Paths Inside the Spiral Corrugation

self-amplification effect of the basic concept behind the spiral corrugator is based on the This results spontaneous radiation. The free electron laser starts with random radiation that is transformed in coherent radiation thanks to the interactions of electrons and the magnetic field inside the wave, in a free-electron laser with a chiral wave, the electrons follow a spiral path Inside the corrugation, thanks to a magnetic field, it is designed to be spiral. This spiral path Electrons emit circularly polarized light radiation. The basic idea Behind the spiral corrugation is the use of magnetic field effect Variable to force the electrons to rotate in a way that allows the generation and amplification of light with high efficiency.

1-The basic equation for the wavelength of the emitted radiation

$$\dot{y}r = \frac{\dot{y}_0}{2Y^2} \left(\frac{1+K^2}{2} \right)$$

Consider a spiral corrugator in the reference frame moving with the axial velocity of the identical beam at the entrance to the corrugator. The FEL core is the corrugator that produces a magnetic field that is constant with time, but varies sinusoidally in space.

$$B B_0 \{ e_x \cos(k_0 z) e_y \sin(k_0 z) \} \\ k_0 = 2\dot{y}/\dot{y}_0 \quad (2.1)$$

B_0 is the amplitude of the magnetic field of the corrugator

$\dot{y}_0$ is the period of the wave

It is a unit vector along the z, y, and x axes $e_y e_x^e$

-The direction of the driving force (Lorentz force) is determined by the directional product between the electron's transverse velocity and the magnetic field of the radiation. When it is present, this direction opposes the axial flow, causing the phases to slow down the electron, where the electrons experience the Lorentz force, carry out transverse oscillations and emit synchrotron radiation in the forward direction

$$F = ma q(EvB) + \dot{y} \quad (2.2)$$

The charge ($\dot{y}$) and the rest mass of the electron (m), in this case the Lorentz force decreases With to

$$F = ma e(vB) \quad (2.3)$$

The relative factor that equals $(1 - \dot{y}x^2)^{1/2} \dot{y}$

Where $\dot{y}$ is the electron accelerator and let the electron move quickly:

$$v e_x v_x e_y v_y e_z v_z \quad (2.4)$$

Using Eq. (2.3) with Eq. (2.1) and Eq. (2.4) and y, X

Ingredients of this power:

$$m_{e\dot{y}} \frac{dv_x}{dt} = ev B_{zy} eB kz\dot{y} \sin_o(0)_z \quad (2.5)$$

$$m_{e\dot{y}} \frac{dv_y}{dt} = ev B_{zx} eB = \dot{y} \cos_o(kz_0v)_z \quad (2.6)$$

Integration by dt gives a wonderful expression

$$vx = \frac{dx}{dt} = \ddot{y}_s \cos(ckz)_0 \quad (2.7)$$

$$vy = \frac{dy}{dt} = \ddot{y}_s \sin(ckz)_0 \quad (2.8)$$

The maximum angle between the electrical path and the ripple axis

$$\ddot{y}_s = K/\ddot{y}$$

Where $K = \frac{eB_0\ddot{y}_0}{2\ddot{y}mc_e}$ represents, and for relative beams, this quantity is less than 1, and k is the corrugation coefficient.

The speed of the electron in this field in c is

$$kzekz = \{\cos(0) \ddot{y} \sin(0)\} + ez_{\ddot{y}z} \quad (2.9)$$

Note that in the case of a wave of the spiral, the axial component of the velocity remains constant V is the transverse velocity of the electron:

$$V_{\ddot{y}} = \ddot{y}_s c \{ex \cos(k_0z) ey \sin(k_0z)\} \quad (2.10)$$

To further integrate (2.7) and eq. (2.8) y,x is given:

$$x = \ddot{y}_s \frac{\ddot{y}_0}{2\ddot{y}} \sin(k_0z) \quad (2.11)$$

$$y = \ddot{y}_s \frac{\ddot{y}_0}{2\ddot{y}} \cos(k_0z) \quad (2.12)$$

$$R(t) = \{e \ddot{y}_s \frac{\ddot{y}_0}{2\ddot{y}} \sin(k_0z) e \ddot{y}_s \frac{\ddot{y}_0}{2\ddot{y}} \cos(k_0z)\} \quad (2.13)$$

This equation gives the extract path of the electron as a function of time as the electron passes through the spiral corrugation of the FEL amplifier, where the radius of the electron pass is:

$$r = \ddot{y}\ddot{y}_{s0}/2\ddot{y} \quad (2.14)$$

The Effect of the Lorentz Constant on the Path of the Electron within the Magnetic Field

Input constants

For the purpose of studying the electron path, we fix these parameters:

The value of the initial relative working current	70 mAh 48
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The following data have also been proven for the application of electromagnetic radiation

Spiral undulation data

Emitted wavelength and laser power rate	11 micrometers 10 megawatts
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The length of the corrugation lo	5.120 meters
The period of the corrugation oy	0.032 meters
The value of the corrugation for the magnetic field oB	0.240 Ts
Ripple constant k	0.72

Program Steps

A specific computer program was used to study the effect of the Lorenz factor by taking into account the data of the path of electrons inside the spiral corrugator with the inputs mentioned previously (figure 3).

Study and Discuss the Impact

When crossing the spiral wave, the electrons will accelerate and emit an electromagnetic wave. This spontaneous emission is the basis of the work of the free electron laser (FEL). A single relativistic electron oscillating in the magnetic field of the undulator will emit radiation in a narrow cone, with the aperture angle for cone

synchrotron, Radiation emission will be included radiation comparable if K is less than one. For cone synchrotron radiation, the emission is mostly in one direction. If K is greater than one, the synchrotron cone sweeps at an angle greater than its aperture. In this case, the spectrum is rich in harmonics and approaches the spectrum of conservation radiation, called the synchrotron.

Figure 3. Program Steps

The magnet is usually referred to as an oscillator, with the wavelength for the k state being less than or equal to one. As we have seen, the relationship of the Lorentz factor is $(\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - \beta^2})$ where β is the ratio of the speed of the electron to the speed of light $= c/v$, and because the

important condition is β , it must be a limited value, Because r is proportional to $(1/\gamma)$ and thus to β , there is an inverse proportionality between r and γ Figure (2-1). Likewise, the effect of the Lorentz factor on the speed of the electron is also an inverse relationship. The electron takes the form: shown in (2-2) The meaning of inverse proportionality is that by increasing the influence of the Lorentz force, the radius of the electron decreases Also, when the effect of the Lorentz force increases, the transverse speed of the electron decreases.

Figure 4. Inverse Relationship between the Lorentz Force and the Radius of the Electron

Figure 5. Inverse Relationship between the Lorentz Force and the Transverse Speed of the Electron

Conclusion

The Lorentz force was simulated and analyzed, and the results showed that the Lorentz force arises from the magnetic field and that the Lorentz force is responsible for generating the laser beam in the free electron laser, as it works to make the electrical charge (electrons) move in the magnetic field. Coherent photons are emitted when an electron acquires an oscillatory motion that speeds it up and slows down depending on the direction of the magnetic field. The Lorentz force can be controlled by the speed of the electrons released from the electron emitter and the resulting change in the strength of the electron's wavelength.

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